

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-4, AUGUST 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

The Role of Vision in *The Faerie Queene*

Nellickal Jacob
Associate Professor,
Dept. of English,
Ramjas College,
University of Delhi.

Article History: Submitted-31/07/2025, Revised-19/08/2025, Accepted-22/08/2025, Published-31/08/2025.

Abstract:

This paper examines the role of sight and the idea of the visual sense in Edmund Spenser's *The Faerie Queene*. It reads the poem as an extended meditation on vision and its ambivalent relationship with truth and knowledge. Spenser's poem demonstrates a deep suspicion of visual surfaces, and this anti-sopic drive often dwells on the deceptive visions that often come in the way of proper understanding. This becomes particularly apparent with *The Faerie Queene*'s representation of women and sexual desire. The article offers a critical account of the poem's investment in the idea of vision and visual objects.

Keywords: Edmund Spenser, *The Faerie Queene*, Visual studies, Gender, Perspective.

The Faerie Queene is a text that invites each generation of readers to discern—from amongst a wealth of textual material that it places on display—patterns of meaning that allow the vast textual space to organise itself into the language of literary-critical intelligibility. This idea of a multi-perspectival, kaleidoscopic set of interpretative possibilities that Spenser's long poem generates is reflected in the fact that literary criticism has over the years adopted manifold critical approaches focusing on different levels of the text. As this paper demonstrates, the poem inscribes into its very body the notion of a point of view that is splintered into multiple threads of intelligibility. By self-consciously thematising the relationship between visibility

and knowledge and conducting a significant exercise on the problematic of sight within the poem, the poem makes visible, through its elaborations on the idea of vision, the difficulty in making sense of the poem through any single interpretative grid.

Arguing for the pre-eminent position that sight enjoys in Spenser's text, Kathleen Williams points out: "Of all the senses, sight is that to which Spenser refers most frequently. The poet sees and exhorts the readers to see; characters in *The Faerie Queene* see or fail to see..." (Williams, 156). The world of *The Faerie Queene* is however one in which the act of seeing is rarely equivalent to the stable, measurable, and ordering gaze of perspectival seeing. Unlike the protocols of perspective vision, which impose visual order and linearity on the visible world, anchoring vision in the safe world of geometrical proportion and realist transparency, Spenser's text seems to exemplify a characterisation of vision that Jonas describes as being

Par excellence the sense of the simultaneous or the co-ordinated, and thereby of the extensive. A view comprehends many things juxtaposed, as co-existent part of one field of vision. It does so in an instant: as in a flash, one glance, an opening of the eyes, discloses a world of co-present qualities spread out in space (Jonas, 136)

In *The Faerie Queene* some of this sense of visual bewilderment that perspectival seeing seeks to organize into a subject-centred world, effectively de-centres the subject of perspective vision through a set of textual devices and strategies. This reading of *The Faerie Queene* will focus on a few thematic strands that bring to the surface the text's attempt to problematize and call into question the idea of a uniform and stable notion of sight, thereby offering a critique of a visual epistemology that equates vision and cognition.

I

Perhaps one of the most striking instances of the text's troubled relationship with the idea of visibility and truth is the constant reiteration of the unreliability of visual surfaces. *The Faerie Queene* frequently demonstrates the need for caution in reading visible signs. This suspicion, that the eye often fails to perceive correctly or that there is a certain naiveté in assuming that the surfaces of the visible convey truths about their interior essences, constantly undermines the ocular confidence that is so often associated with perspectival seeing.

This anti-scopic discourse is most evident in the thematics of *seeming* that present, for the characters of *The Faerie Queene* as well as for the reader, an acute epistemological and representational problem. The very first adventure that the Redcrosse knight and Una encounter in their travels is a result of the failure to *see* the gap between the *seeming* world of appearances and the dangers that lurk hidden beneath such exteriors. Seeking refuge in Errours den that, “Faire harbour that them seems” (*Faerie Queene*, 1.1.7), they soon find themselves facing their first challenge, “That makes them doubt, their wits be not their owne” (*Faerie Queene* 1.1.10). One of the early lessons in visuality that the Redcrosse Knight learns to be wary of is the danger of spaces that blot out the possibility of sight. In the case of Errour, the negation of light and vision are seen as directly connected to the principle of evil that she represents: “For light she hated as the deadly bale/ Ay wont in deadly darknes to remaine,/ Where plaine none might her see, nor she see any plaine” (*Faerie Queene* 1.1.16). Evil is clearly more potent when cloaked from view: “Worse is daunger hidden, then descried” (*Faerie Queene* 2. 12. 35)

Nevertheless, visual data have the potential to both clarify and confound. Entering into Lucifera's court in the House of Pryde, they find their senses overwhelmed by the “sumptuous shew...whose glorious view/ their frayle amazed senses did confound” (*Faerie Queene* 1. 4.7). However, in Book II, when Arthur meets Pyrhochles and Cymochles dishonouring the

unconscious body of Guyon, he can visually discern the fact of Guyon's innocence. This act of seeing gauges moral worth through reading exteriors with the assumption that they yield up truths about character. He is therefore able to fight on behalf of Guyon, "In whose dead face he redd great magnanimity" (*Faerie Queene* 2.8.23). However, this feature of surfaces as reflections of inner worth is a visual convention that can never be taken for granted. As every visual sign has the potential "To seeme like truth" (*Faerie Queene* 1.7.1), the world of *The Faerie Queene* displays characters who often stumble and fall as they journey through the visual terrain of the poem.

The ubiquitous presence of misleading and confounding surfaces that present themselves to the eye also highlights the double-edged nature of representation itself. In a world that is grappling with the idea of both the dynamics of self-representation and the potentially radical falsehoods that artistic representation was alleged to stand for, Spenser's text offers many moments that seem to betray an anxiety about the danger of representation being usurped for the purposes of deception. This wilful manipulation of signs he most often connects with women, who use art as a means to project beguiling images of themselves. Seeming to be what they are not, they employ visual spectacle to good effect in order to achieve their ends. Their extraordinary success reveals not just the wealth of visual arts and contrivances that they have access to, but also demonstrates the power of images and the inordinate value attached to them in the world of *The Faerie Queene*. The elaborate visual spectacle of Lucifera's court in the House of Pryde conceals the fact of her illegitimate claim to power: "Yet rightfull kingdome she had none at all, / Ne heritage of natiue souerantie, / But did vsurpe with wrong and tyrannie" (*Faerie Queene* 1.4.12). Philotime, to whom Guyon is conveyed by Mammon, is similarly able to use art as a means to "cloke her crime" and pretend to possess a degree of beauty that "Yet was not that same her owne natiue hew, / But wrought by art and counterfitted shew, / Thereby more louers unto her call" (*Faerie Queene* 2.6.45). In both the case of Lucifera

and Philotime a measure of the success of their attempts to appear spectacular is the number of people that seem to throng their courts clamouring for recognition. Furthermore, the visual positioning of their bodies high above the people is carefully staged to obtain maximum advantage.

However, it is Duessa who epitomizes the principle of dissimulation. She too uses visual effects to conceal her real self. This is interestingly conceived of as a reflection of her moral corruption in the vocabulary of visual disfigurement. Appearing first before the Red Crosse Knight as a “Lady clad in scarlot red, / Purpled with gold and pearle of rich assay” she accompanies Sans foy entertaining him “with faire disport and courting dalliance”(*Faerie Queene* 1.2. 13,14). Claiming for herself the identity of Fidessa (“cloked with Fidessals name”) (*Faerie Queene* 1.7.1), she is quick to adapt her appearance to fit her new role: “With Le rest pefe) change of chear the seeming simple maid. / Let fallen her eien, as shamefast to the earth”(*Faerie Queene* 1.2.27). Describing herself as, “I that do seeme not I, Duessa ame,”(*Faerie Queene* 1.5.26), she represents not merely the idea of deception and false seeming but is also integrally connected to the absence of light, a Daughter of Night who is a “dreary Dame, of darknes Queene” (*Faerie Queene* 1.5.24). Her stripping in Canto VIII visually reiterates the radical falsehood of visual surfaces. Beneath the “scarlot robe... And ornaments that richly were displayed”—the visual accessories that she uses for deceiving the spectator—Duessa conceals another kind of visual spectacle, “Which when the knights beheld, amazed they were”(*Faerie Queene* 1.8.49). This aspect of a radical reversal of visual appearances from the embodiment of beauty to the visualisation of monstrosity serves to articulate Spenser's visual field, the boundaries of which, as I will demonstrate later on in the article, fade into invisibility.

The manufacture of images is a task that finds its most powerful embodiment in the figure of Archimago, who as his name suggests, is a maker of images. Using “magick bookes and arts of sundrie kindes”(*Faerie Queene* 1.1.36), Archimago can conjure up forms and images that

are calculated to beguile the senses, primarily of vision. Introduced in Book I as a man who looks scholarly, melancholic, and innocuous: “Sober he seemde and full sagely sad, / And to the ground his eyes were lowly bent”(*Faerie Queene* 1.1.29), he is adept both at switching between various roles that help him achieve his ends, and capable of producing and directing illusions to aid him in his schemes. Archimago is also a wordsmith of rare qualities. Spinning a host of narratives to incite revenge and violence, he can use language to great advantage. Having under his mastery the means of using representation, both verbal and visual, Archimago demonstrates through all his machinations the extremely manipulable and malleable nature of the sign. In many ways, curiously reflective of the image of the artist/poet, he thrives on the lack of closure in language that allows him to constantly re-ascribe and reinvent meanings to suit his schemes. Describing him as a man who “of pleasing wordes had store”, Spenser goes on to use a fascinating image to describe his facility with language: “And well could file his tongue as smooth as glas”(*Faerie Queene* 1. 1. 35). The metaphor here suggests the complexity of Archimago's talents—he is shown to be so skilled with language that it takes on the smooth transparency of glass through which one looks. Here, the evocative power of his language is shown as being on par with the transparent realism of the image. Word and image collapse into one another to produce pure illusion.

For Archimago, Una represents the very anti-thesis of himself and is therefore a special target for his “diuelish arts”. Representing oneness and truth, Una embodies the principle of unfeigned expression in direct contrast to the multiplicity of roles and meanings that are the special province of Archimago. It is thus that he devotes himself to devising. “How he may worke vnto her further smarts: / For he hated her as the hissing snake” (*Faerie Queene* 1.2. 9).

It is ironic that the designer of false images is not immune to the instability and duplicity of the sign. Unable to detect the cowardly Braggadochio who masks his true nature under the trappings of knighthood, Archimago allows himself to fall prey to the crude manipulation of

symbols that Braggadochio is capable of: “Who seeing one that shone in armour fayre, / On goodly courser thondering with his feet, / Eftsoones supposed him a person meet” (*Faerie Queene* 1.3.11). This testifies to both the indecipherability of signs and the fact that images can distort reality in ways that seem to exempt nobody from their deceptive appearances.

Nowhere is the full range of “subtill” Archimago's genius for representation and image creation more in evidence than in Book I when he takes the Red Crosse Knight and Una to the “lowly Hermitage” to spend the night. Here he begins by using language to charm them before “drownd in deadly sleepe he findes” (*Faerie Queene* 1.1.36). This done, he consults “His magick bookes and artes of sundrie kindes” to discover a way to work “mighty charms, to trouble sleepy minds”(I. i. 36). Calling up spirits from the “deepe darknes”, he chooses two “the falsest twoo / And fittest for to forge true-seeming lyes”(*Faerie Queene* 1.1.38). He then proceeds to orchestrate a complex series of illusions that seem specially designed to penetrate the defences of the Red Crosse knight. The illusions are aimed at bringing to the surface and making visible, traces of desires and anxieties that clearly function as the repressed in the chivalric code that is operative among the knights of Gloriana. Carefully calculated to insert themselves into the interstices between consciousness and the unconscious, Archimago's illusions are craftily constructed to multiply their effects on their subjects through the staging and re-staging of ‘true-seeming’ images during different states of consciousness.

The text of Archimago's illusion opens out onto different levels in Red Crosse's mind. The first stage involves the gentle introduction of the dream image of the false Una into the mind of the Red Crosse who sleeps “soundly void of euil thought”(*Faerie Queene* 1.1.46). This image of a Una who lies beside him without the restraint and modesty he is accustomed to, speaking in a manner that is suggestive of love and sexual feelings, causes a perturbation even in his dream state. He awakens from his dream to witness another level of the illusion. This time he sees before him Una, appearing even more clearly expressive of her desire for him—

the implicit sexual energy of the earlier dream now brought to the surface in the image of a sexually uninhibited Una “halfe blushing offr[ing] him to kis, /with gentle blandishment and louely looke”(*Faerie Queene* 1.1. 49). There is an interesting transference outwards here from the first level of the dream state to the second. In the first level he dreams of being roused to consciousness, finding himself greatly confounded by the sudden awareness of unacknowledged sexual feelings which he perceives of as being “unwonted lust”. The second level however succeeds in externalising this “wonted feare of doing ought amis”, by projecting it on to the image of Una who now presents the “vncouth sight” of a woman of “noble blood” employing “shamelesse guise” to seduce her lover. Using flattery, the false Una steals her way past his defences until he lapses back into a dream that “gan freshly tosse his braine, / With bowres, and beds, and ladies deare delight”(*Faerie Queene* 1.1. 55). His attempts to resist the temptations offered to him end on an ambiguous note: “But when he saw his labour was all vaine, / With that misformed spright he backe returned againe” (*Faerie Queene* 1.1.55). The illusionary dream state is interrupted by the breaking of daylight, which drives Archimago to organize the third level of the illusion—an act of desperation to concretize the ambivalent success of the first two levels. This time, Archimago employs a purely optical image that now appears to seamlessly connect with the visions in the dream. The dream feeds into the sensory experience of empirical sight, fuelling and bringing to a head the desires that are invoked through the dream. This time the falsely conjured sight of Una in passionate sexual embrace with a young squire, “In wanton lust and leud embracement,” causes Red Crosse to abandon all scepticism about the validity of what he *see* and spurs him on to desert Una and leave without further ado. On this occasion Red Crosse sees a completely materialized vision of desire, now externalized fully in the copulating bodies of Una and the squire. Although implicated in the very act of looking (“guilty sight”), it is on the basis of this that he is able to take decisive action and leave. Thus Archimago succeeds in his project of having Red Crosse

and Una “diuide into double parts,” an accomplishment that validates the power of his “devilish arts” (*Faerie Queene* 1.2.9).

It is crucial to note the different visual protocols that are employed here in the production of the illusion. By creating a complex weave between dream *seeing* and empirical vision, Archimago creates a visual sequence that progresses towards an illusory seeing which is made possible by the gradual beguiling of the eye through successive stages of dream vision. By the last level, Red Crosse literally sees what Archimago wishes him to see, a feat that is made possible by a careful blurring of distinctions between the different visual states that are deployed. The insubstantial sights of the dream state are both validated by sensory sight as well as used to call into question the radical insubstantiality of empirical vision. If all visual texts are merely fictive shadows pretending to yield up truth to the eyes of the observer, how then does one distinguish between the orders of truth and falsehood? The dream fades into reality, deconstructing the difference between appearance and reality.

Spenser's depiction of the dialogue between visibility and truth therefore does not find its resolution in the familiar binarisms of appearance and reality but seem to be actively engaged in decentring the very grounds for such a dialectics.

II

The *Faerie Queene's* preoccupation with visuality is also evident in the manner in which it deals with the representation of sexuality. On the face of it, Spenser buys into the dominant representations of sexuality that articulate sexual desire in the language of vision and map sexuality onto an ocular grid that assigns different positions for men and women in terms of their relationship to visibility. In this system, women are perceived as the visually consumable body that feeds the legitimate or illegitimate gaze of men. Their value in this scale of visibility however is calculated on their ability to resist visual access to their bodies through the exercise

of virtue. The chaste woman is therefore one who like Una can conceal more than reveal. On the other hand, for a woman to self-consciously either assert or strategically withhold her sexuality would be a breach of patriarchal protocols.

Unlike Una, who conceals her body from view through the careful attention she pays to her veil and "blacke stole", a number of women in the poem are shown to effectively use the art of making their bodies a spectacle for all to see. Like Lucifera and Philotime they transform their bodies into visual spectacles, and like Duessa they use visual symbols to pretend to virtue which they do not possess. The numerous images of such women reflect, as Cavanagh points out, "a nervousness about potential female dissembling, an apparent belief in the difficulty of distinguishing between *good* and *evil* women" (Cavanagh, 29). The ambiguous quality of female bodies underscored by their ability to appeal to the "fyrie lustful eye[s]" (*Faerie Queene* 1.6.4) re-iterates their instability as visual signs. To allow oneself to be seduced by their visual charms, Spenser suggests, is to be trapped in the superficial, morally dubious realm of externalities. To do so would be to partake of a form of looking that produces a desiring gaze, which fails to provide satiety. This kind of sight is described as the sterile voyeuristic gaze, "Of hungry eies, which n'ote therewith be filled" (*Faerie Queene* 2.12.78).

Beneath the unstable and potentially dangerous visual signs that women's bodies are associated with, there is a profound ambivalence about women that manifests itself once again in terms of the limits of visibility. In many ways expressive of the visual paradigm that governs the practices of looking in *The Faerie Queene*, women and the kinds of gaze they invite form the very units of the visual discourse in the poem. The visual field thereby articulated by the idea of women as visible symbols finds itself coming up against its limits in two different ways.

One such boundary of visuality appears in the imagining of the dissembling female body shorn of its cloak of pretence. This dramatic moment in the text occurs in the stripping of

Duessa in Book I. The impulse behind the act is in some senses to visually apprehend the actual image of the female body to peel back the surface of the body in order to violently grasp its inner truths. This act of attempting to forcefully impose the need for having the relationship between surfaces and depths revealed on the female body, is conducted as a violent visual exercise to so that “Such as she was, their eies might behold” (*Faerie Queene* 1.8.46).

The results of the stripping are conveyed using an extreme visual language that seeks to graphically describe the body as monstrous. Using old age, bodily deformation, and the language of sexual revulsion, the description re-enacts the male gaze in travelling from her head downwards. However, the picturing of the stripped female form fails in its project and reaches the limits of its imaginative powers, especially in the inability to picture the female sexual organs. This inability to articulate the body fully, which Cavanagh describes as “a perpetual fear of female genitalia in Spenser, occupies the unspeakable of the discourse of visuality” (Cavanagh, 29).

This visual limit beyond which the language of representation fails to image forth meaning finds an interesting counterpart in another kind of unrepresentability that of representing the sovereign (“Great Ladie of the greatest Isle”) to whom the poem is dedicated. The Queen is described as being the source of light who has the power to impregnate the “feeble eyne” of the poet with the power of poetic vision, which is directly connected to an enhancement of cognitive powers as well: “raise my thoughts too humble and too vile” (*Faerie Queene* Proem, 1.4). Being the vision endowing source “whose light / Like Phoebus lampe throughout the world doth shine”, her association with light is mirrored in the description of Arthur, whose shield, when uncovered, gives off a “light whereof, that heuens light did pas, /Such blazing brightnesse through the ayre threw/That eye mote not the same endure to vew” (*Faerie Queene* 1.7.34). The positive light that they emanate has the power to clarify vision and negate the principle of the hidden and the cloaked. Before Arthur's shield “all that was not such, as seemed

in sight, / Before that shield did fade, and suddeine fall”(*Faerie Queene* 1.7.35). However, paradoxically, this light also has the potential for blinding and therefore represents the very limits of visibility. Powerful sources of light can also at the same time cancel out the possibility of sight. This paradox is also evident in the poem's attempts to picture the Queen. Expressing scepticism “if pourtrayd it might bee by any living art” the poet goes on to say:

But living art may not least part expresse,
Nor life-resembling pencill it can paynt,
His daedale hand would faile, and greatly faynt,
And her perfections with his error taynt:
Ne Poets witt, that passeth Paintr farre...

For fear through want of words her excellence to marre (*Faerie Queene*, Proem. 3).

Located at the outer limit of representation, the act of 'picturing' the Queen is doomed to be an incomplete and impossible project.

It is interesting therefore that both the limits that define the very possibility of visualization are the bodies of the Queen and the duplicitous Duessa who in different ways define the boundaries of representation. The imaging of the female body therefore establishes the discursive limits that structure the field of vision in ways that are articulated through the thematics of purity, sexuality, and *seeming*.

III

An alternate vocabulary of conceiving vision that the poem repeatedly accesses is the use of mirrors and the kinds of visions that it makes possible. Used by Lucifera in the House of Pryde to feed her vanitie, the mirror is eminently available for the project of narcissism.

However, mirrors also have other functions. In the case of Britomart in Book III the magic mirror provides her with a vision of Artegall whose pictured form she falls in love with. But perhaps the most interesting function of the mirror is its ability to go beyond the spatial and reflective and gain an insight into temporality. The mirror reveals the future to Britomart and in doing so achieves a new dimension of vision. Vision is no longer caught between the dialectics of truth and falsity, but bursts through the visual present to the visionary act of seeing the future.

The poetic elaboration of vision in Spenser's *The Faerie Queene* therefore opens up a number of questions about sight and perspective all of which resonate through the poem making it imperative for critical perspectives on the poem to reflect on the problematic seeing—both within the poem and in what we *see* the poem to be.

Works Cited:

Cavanagh, Shiela T. *Wanton Eyes and Chaste Desires: Female Sexuality in the The Faerie Queene*. Indiana University Press, 1994.

Jonas, Hans. *The Phenomenon of Life: Towards a Philosophical Biology*. University of Chicago Press, 1982.

Spenser, Edmund. *The Faerie Qveene*, edited by A. C. Hamilton, Longman, 2001.

Williams, Kathleen, “Spenser and the Metaphor of Sight.” *Rice University Studies*, vol 60. no 2. 1969, pp 153-169.